

Scurvy during Henry Middleton's Voyage (1604)

by Harri Hemilä

In 1604, Henry Middleton commanded a voyage to the East Indies, during which scurvy occurred. This document presents excerpts describing the outbreak.

Biography:

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henry_Middleton_\(captain\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henry_Middleton_(captain))

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ref:odnb/18673>

[https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Dictionary_of_National_Biography,_1885-1900/Middleton,_Henry_\(d.1613\)](https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Dictionary_of_National_Biography,_1885-1900/Middleton,_Henry_(d.1613))

Yellow is used to indicate more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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The earliest recorded outbreak of scurvy on a long sea voyage seems to have occurred during Vasco da Gama's first voyage to India (1497-1499).¹ Thereafter, the disease afflicted vast numbers of sailors throughout the Age of Sail.^{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12} In the English Navy, the incidence of scurvy declined dramatically at the end of the eighteenth century, when lemon juice was made obligatory for seamen.^{4, 13, 14}

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- 1 Scurvy during Vasco da Gama's first voyage (1497-1499).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/46440>
 - 2 Lind J (1772) A Treatise on the Scurvy.
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/n5/mode/2up>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt>
 - 3 Rouppe L (1772) On the Scurvy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17227637> Rouppe
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302180> Lind's summary
 - 4 Kenneth J Carpenter (1986) The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C: The explorers' sickness; p.1-28,95-97.
<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>
 - 5 Scurvy during Magellan's voyage around the world (1519-1522).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001193>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/42884> Translation by Robertson
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/74723> Translation by Stanley
 - 6 Scurvy during Thomas Stevens' voyage to India (1579).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174375>
 - 7 Scurvy on John Davis' voyage (1591-1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17884408>
 - 8 Scurvy during Richard Hawkins' voyage (1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>
 - 9 Scurvy during Sebastián Vizcaíno's exploration (1602-1603).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18300855> Ascensión
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18301146> Lind's summary
 - 10 Francois Pyrard's Description of Scurvy During a Sea Voyage (1602-1603).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18415628>
 - 11 Scurvy on Anson's voyage round the world (1740-1744).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397300>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/16611>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/47130>
 - 12 A fatal scurvy in the East Indies (1762).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299146>
 - 13 Budd G (1840) Scurvy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>
 - 14 Between the years 1779 and 1813, the diminution of sick and of deaths in the British navy was in the proportion of four to one. In 1779, 1:2.45 were sick, and in 1813, 1:10.75 were sick, corresponding to decline by ratio 4.4.
Table 1, p.539-540 in:
Blane G (1815) Statements of the comparative Health of the British Navy, from the year 1779 to the year 1814.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2129027>

In his authoritative book "*The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*", Kenneth Carpenter⁴ (1986, p.18-19) writes about Middleton's voyage as follows:

A second expedition was sent out by the English East India Company in 1604 under Sir Henry Middleton. They sailed on March 25 and on May 16 they were at the Equator, "where many of our men fell sick of the scurvy, calenture [tropical fever], bloody flux [dysentery], and the worms; being left to the mercy of God, and a small quantity of lemon juice every morning..." By July 13, when they were off the Cape, there were

at least 80 men sick of the scurvy in our ship... The general commanded the tacks aboard, intending to go about the Cape [i.e., to continue the voyage without landing there] but our sick men cried out most lamentably... made a petition to the general, most humbly entreating him for God's sake to save their lives, and to put in for Saldania, otherwise they were but dead men. The general perusing their pitiful complaint, and looking out of his cabin door, where did attend a swarm of lame and weak diseased cripples, and beholding this lamentable sight extended his compassion towards them, and granted their requests.

The original report does not add substantially to the above extract by Carpenter.

The voyage of Sir Henry Middleton to Bantam and the Maluco Islands

<https://archive.org/details/voyagesirhenrym00corngoog/page/n37/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/voyageofsirhenry0000midd/page/n47/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/voyageofsirhenry00middrich/page/4/mode/2up>

The next day the general would not go a-land, but sent captain Stiles, captain Keeling, and captain Middleton, with express order to keep their people from straggling;¹⁵ and when all their company were landed, captain Stiles called them all together, giving them warning to keep company together, and not range one from the other; which speech was reiterated again by master Durham, saying that whosoever was found straggling should be severely punished, and therefore willed them all to take good heed. And so, after this warning given, they marched up into the country to kill some goats, where they met with two *Portugals*, which did assist them in all *the* [their] might. In the meanwhile they were at their sport a-land, the general with the rest were busy in stowing the Hector's long boat, for that he was minded to go to sea so soon as they had done; but they could not stow her without cutting off her stem and part of her bows, which, seeing no other way, was presently effected. And so, drawing towards night, our land-men repaired aboard with some few goats they had killed; and after supper, the wind coming off the land, the general gave order to the master to weigh [anchor], and that a warning-piece might be shot off—and so presently the cable was brought to capstan, and our ship was presently loose; but before we had up our anchor, captain Stiles sent word one of their merchants was missing: so that we came presently to anchor again, and did ride till day. He that lost himself was the party [master Durham] which was so careful to give other men warning, which took none himself. Day no sooner appearing but the general sent captain Stiles, with at least one hundred and fifty men, to seek for him; and if it were possible to speak with some of the *Portugals*, but all that day was spent in vain, and no news of him; so the general would spend no longer time there, but left him to learn the language! So the sixteenth of May we passed the line, where **many of our men fell sick of the scurvy**, calenture, bloody flux, and the worms; being left to the mercy of God, and a small quantity of lemon-juice.¹⁶

p.5

p.6

¹⁵ <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/straggle>

¹⁶ The deficiency of *lemon-juice* was an unfortunate oversight. Captain Lancaster had proved its importance. "The reason why the generals men stood better in health then the men of other ships, was this: he brought to sea with him certaine bottles of the iuice of limons—by this meanes the generall cured many of his men, and preserued the rest."—Purchas.

every morning: our physician, shipped for that purpose, being as unwilling as ignorant in anything that might help them—a great oversight in the company, and no doubt will be better looked to hereafter.

p.7

And to our *proceeding* voyage: the thirteenth day of July, being Friday, we had sight of Cape Boa Esperança [the Cape of Good Hope]. The wind at south-west, a gentle gale, the general commanded the tacks aboard, intending to go about the Cape, but our sick men cried out most lamentably, for at that present there were sick of the scurvy at the least eighty men in our ship, not one able to help the other, who made a petition to the general, most humbly entreating him for God's sake to save their lives, and to put in for *Saldania*,¹⁷ otherways they were but dead men. The general perusing their pitiful complaint, and looking out of his cabin door, where did attend a swarm of lame and weak diseased cripples, who beholding this lamentable sight extended his compassion towards them, and granted their requests.¹⁸ That night the wind came up at the south, and continued till the seventeenth day before we could get into the road.¹⁹ The next morning, being Wednesday, the general went on land, with provision to set up tents; and a little way from our landing-place, the negroes had their houses—which were no other than a few crooked sticks set in the ground, and mats cast over them — and they had great store of cattle, both beeves and sheep, grazing *fair by* them.²⁰ Our general and the captains went to barter with them for small pieces of iron, and bought some twelve sheep, and more would have sold us till that they saw us begin to set up our tents, which as it seemed was to their disliking, for that, incontinent, they pulled down their houses and made them fast upon their beasts' backs, and did drive away; yet all means possible was sought to draw them to sell us more, but in no case they would abide any longer with us, but drove away with all the speed they might. It lay in the general's power to have taken them all from them, as some counselled him to do, but he in no case would give ear thereunto, but let them depart, not doubting but that they would return again, seeing we offered them no wrong when it was in our powers to dispossess them of all their cattle.

p.8

The nineteenth day we got our sick men on land, and the twentieth our boats were sent to the island, where we found such infinite number of seals that it was admirable to behold! all the sea-shore lies over-spread with them, some sleeping, some travelling into the island, and some to the seaward;

17 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saldanha,_South_Africa

18 The general was authorised to refresh at *St. Lawrence*, now called Madagascar, but “not at *Saldania* in anywise.” The probable reason for this injunction appears in a subsequent note.—*Instructions*, § 6.

19 *The Ascension*. “The seventeenth day we came to anchor in the road of Saldanha, having sixty men sick of the scurvy; but, God be praised, they all recovered health before we went from hence.”—T. Clayborne.

20 *Fair by* must mean *conveniently near*. The expression occurs about ten times, and seems always to have the same import.

besides all the rocks which lie a pretty distance off, so full as they can hold—thousands at a time going and as many coming out: there be many of them as big as any bear, and as terrible to behold. And up towards the middle of the island there be infinite numbers of fowls called penguins, pelicans, and cormorants. The penguins be as big as our greatest capons we have in England; they have no wings, nor cannot fly, but you may drive them by thousands in a flock whither you will. They be exceeding fat, but their flesh is very rank, for that they live upon fish: there be so many of them upon this small island, which is not above five miles about, to lade a ship of fifty tons withal.

p.9

Upon Sunday, the twenty-third, **the first man that died out of our ship.** Upon Monday morning the general went into the country to buy fresh victuals, but the people of the country, seeing so many in company, fled. But the general caused all the company to make a stand, and then sent four to them with a bottle of wine and victuals, with a tabor and a pipe. They seeing no more in company came to them, and did eat, drink, and dance with them; so they, seeing with what kindness they were used, took heart unto them, and came along with our general to our tents; where they had many toys bestowed upon them, as pins, points, beads, and branches—and so they returned all very well pleased, making signs to return the next day with cattle; but foul weather prevented them for three days. The fourth day after, being the twenty-sixth, they brought us forty-four sheep, and the next day twenty-three sheep and two kine,²¹ and the next day fifteen sheep and one bullock,²² and the thirtieth day we bought one-hundred-and-twenty sheep and six beeves,²³ the next day nine sheep and three beeves, and the second of August three sheep.

...

This night, and the next after, our sentinels had spied the country people lurking about our tents, so that alarum²⁴ was given, and they fled. Upon the fourteenth of August we departed all aboard our ships, where we rode till the nineteenth, the wind not serving to carry us out, which then served our turns; we put to sea, and stood to the westward, and the twenty-fifth day we doubled the Cape of Good Hope, with very favorable winds till the fifth of September, and after that time we met with the wind scarce, and now

p.14

p.15

21 Kine. Plural of cow.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/kine>

22 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/bullock>

23 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/beeve>

24 The former edition has *alarome*. The word was thus defined: “*Alarum*. An out-cry signifying, To your arms.”—*English Expositor*.

and then calms; and here began the scurvy to grow amongst our men, and every day did the disease increase.²⁵ Here might somewhat be said of the ignorance and uncharitableness of him that was shipped for our physician, as a caveat to them that shall go hereafter to be better provided; but for two respects I forbear—the one in regard of his other calling, but chiefly for that he is since dead in the voyage, where, for my part, I wish his faults may be buried with him.²⁶

The nineteenth of December we had sight of Engano, an island lying near Sumatra; the twentieth we had sight of Sumatra; the twenty-first we anchored within the islands, where we were put to great trouble to have up our yards and get up our anchors. Our men were exceeding weak; we were fain to send men out of our ship to help the rest, and so with much ado we came to Bantam road. The occasion why we first anchored was, because the Ascension shot off a piece of ordnance within night, which was contrary to our articles; we, doubting she was in some great distress, came suddenly to an anchor to tarry to know what was the matter, which proved to be nothing but that their gunner was dead and thrown overboard, and had that piece for a farewell; which folly of theirs put us to great trouble, causing us to anchor in the sea in twenty-five fathoms, then winds all westerly, which brought in a great Seagate,²⁷ that the next day morning we had much ado to get up our anchor; and as for the other ships, they were not able to weigh without our helps, which we sent them; and so, with very much trouble, we got us all under sail, steering away east-and-by-north and east-north-east till we came to anchor between the island and the main, at the entrance of Bantam Bay, in seven fathoms, sandy ground.

p.16

25 The scurvy is clearly indicated in the *Roteiro* of the voyage of Vasco da Gama in 1497; and it is the earliest notice of it which I can call to memory. At the period now in question, it prevailed to a frightful extent.—*Roteiro*; Jean Moequet; Sir R. Hawkins; etc.

[See footnotes 1-11]

26 After refreshing, the general was to shape his course *direct* for Bantam; and as he had put into Saldanha Bay contrary to *express order*, and staid there five weeks, he crossed the Indian Ocean without touching at Madagascar.—*Instructions*, § 7.

27 *Seagate* means the *swell of the sea*. Example: “The best ground [for ships] to ride in, is— where they may ride land-locked, so as that the *sea-gate* can have no power against them.”—Sir H. Manwayring.